

The promotion of new edible packaging: A plastic-free future

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Abstract

Landfill disposal is significantly more expensive and causes a carbon footprint that is harmful to humans and the environment due to excessive use of plastic that takes millennia to break down than using a biodegradable and environmentally friendly product that can be easily dissolved. To address this issue, the researchers intend to launch the new edible food packaging and promote it in the food industry in Bacoor, Cavite. The researchers coordinated with Ecobiertos Tapioca-rice Straws, a company that produces edible food containers such as cups and straws, and the company that will be promoted in this study. The respondents in the study were 25 fast-food customers and 25 fast-food managers because they have knowledge of food. A quantitative approach was used to collect data by sending a survey questionnaire. Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions, the researchers observed that changes must be made in food establishments in the Philippines, and operational alterations would make the environment refrain from degradation in the long run. The researchers recommend enhancing future research in the food industry, addressing specific weak points, and recognizing that the current study should broaden our understanding of and ability to recognize environmental components in innovating products, especially with plastic, and deepen the understanding of how plastic is transported between components and improve knowledge of its effect in the environment.

Keywords: *Edible packaging; Tapioca rice; Straw; Biodegradable.*

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Introduction

Drinking straws have traditionally been designed to be a disposable item, and numerous countries, regions, and municipalities have outlawed single-use plastic straws to minimize plastic pollution. Some businesses have voluntarily eliminated or reduced the number of plastic straws distributed on their premises. Thermoplastic polymer polypropylene is often used to produce the most common type of drinking straw. This plastic is well-known for its resilience, light weight, and low cost of manufacture (Malpass & Band, 2012). Furthermore, polyvinyl chloride (PVC) is also used in producing plastic straws, which are all dangerous to the environment (Viera et al., 2020).

In terms of the countries that are top ten emitters of oceanic plastic pollution and plastic straws, China, Indonesia, the Philippines, Vietnam, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Egypt, Malaysia, Nigeria, and Bangladesh are included (Jambeck et al., 2015). Plastic drinking straw manufacture generates a negligible amount to petroleum consumption, while used straws contribute a negligible amount to global plastic pollution when discarded. The image of a plastic straw caught in a sea turtle's nostril, which immediately traveled across all kinds of media, also helped to raise awareness about the possible dangers of plastic straws to marine life.

Products with new edible packaging materials should be promoted for their ease of use and distinctiveness. As a result, an edible food packaging product does not always need to be expensive. Edible food packaging has found a lot of success in recent years. The benefit of this packaging is that it may be safely eaten as part of a food product while also being environmentally beneficial and increasing the shelf life of fresh products. This edible packaging in the food packaging sector provides a novel method of eating food and beverages and studies the industry's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats, segmentation, and target market.

The new edible packaging materials may be characterized arbitrarily as thin layers of material that can be consumed by the consumer as part of the whole food product. Edible packaging must be as bland and feasible as a food component to be identified during the intake of the edible packaged food product. Edible packaging is not as new as some believe, as research into it has been ongoing for decades. Most people believe that because their package will disappear in nature, tossing it anywhere is fine. Then there is the problem of customers who are unwilling to eat from their utensils or food package. They may be cautious about the sanitary features of edible packaging, such as whether it prevents food from contamination as well as normal packing.

While edible packaging has a long way to go before it becomes the standard rather than the exception, it is a much more environmentally friendly alternative to single-use food packaging. The problem is that many individuals are already aware of how harmful plastic is to our environment and our surroundings. Plastic takes a millennium to degrade regardless of where it is disposed, and it is most disposed in landfills. That means that apart from the trivial amount that has been recycled; all plastic that has ever been manufactured is still there in landfills. To address this issue, the researchers conducted a study to encourage the use of innovative edible packaging materials in the Philippines and to aid Ecobiertos.

The related literature and studies gathered strongly support the study on the significance of developing a solution to address the problem of plastic waste that contributes to global warming, which is now a global concern (Chen et al., 2019; Makaremi et al., 2019; Rai et al., 2019; Motelica et al., 2020). Studies agree that there are innovative ways to reduce plastic waste, like raising the percentage of recyclable materials and enhancing the proportion of compostable and/or biodegradable materials in packaging and containers (Hanani et al., 2014; Ivonkovic et al., 2017; Mir et al., 2018; Yanti et al., 2021). The proposed edible packaging also supports the expected healthful benefits and characteristics of healthy food packaging, which is biodegradable and ecofriendly and concerns the preservation and protection of all types of foods. This concludes the most practical option of all to simply be responsible for maintaining the product's quality and freshness while extending the shelf life of food products and overcoming the environmental problems of wasting packaging at the same time (Gheorghita et al., 2020).

Other campaigns to jumpstart the edible packaging movements are also in the works. LoliWare, for example, creates edible agar-based cups, while WikiCells is working on a shell that can hold foods and drinks manufactured from food particles. Both have drawbacks in that their key constituents are more expensive and add to the overall cost of the finished product, making sustainability with present techniques more challenging. In the future, the goal is to develop packaging that can contain single-serve foods. Of course, there are challenges in implementing this type of packaging, as there are concerns regarding shelf life as well as mold and germ safety.

The researchers employed a quantitative analysis to widen the scope of the study, which is intended to promote new edible materials. The purpose of this research is to demonstrate that edible food packaging benefits the food sector, and to promote the most recent edible stuff in the Philippines, which is the tapioca-rice starch straw.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to promote edible packaging as an eco-friendly alternative food packaging since plastic, while being the best food packaging and container at the same time, takes thousands of years to degrade, and is toxic to both the environment and the humans. The following questions addressed in this study are the following:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age and gender?
2. What is the level of awareness of the respondents in terms of edible packaging?
3. How does the respondent assess the characteristics of edible food packaging in terms of?
 - 3.1 Taste
 - 3.2 Odor
 - 3.3 Texture
 - 3.4 Smell
 - 3.5 Appearance
4. What are the strategies needed to develop to promote edible food packaging?

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, a quantitative design was adopted. Furthermore, the approach used must be consistent with the study's aims and solve the problem. Quantitative research, according to Bryman (2016), is a research strategy that stresses the quantification of data gathering and interpretation. The researcher analyzes the data with statistics in the hopes of obtaining an unbiased result that can be applied to a larger population (Glesne, 2014). The results of the quantitative data gathering approach were compiled into a single data set that included a Likert scale for their opinions on edible packaging.

Table 1. Level of interpretation

Range	Verbal Interpretation
4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree
3.41-4.20	Agree
2.61-3.40	Neutral
1.81-2.60	Disagree
1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree

Respondents used a Likert scale to express their level of agreement or disagreement with a set of propositions on a balanced agree-disagree scale (Burns & Burns, 2011). In this case, they rate their perceptions of edible packaging, as well as the product's sustainability and likelihood of using the edible straw more frequently.

Locale of the Study

This study was carried out in the city of Bacoor, Cavite province. The following are the chosen eateries: Jollibee, McDonald's, Chowking, KFC, Botejyu, Tender Bob's, Burger King, Max's Restaurant, and Kuya J's, which are some of the most popular fast-food restaurants in the Philippines. Jollibee, McDonald's, Chowking, KFC, Botejyu, Tender Bob's, Burger King, and Max's Restaurant are among the restaurants and fast-food franchises found at SM Bacoor, whereas SM Molino features the same list of restaurants except Kuya J's.

Figure 1. Restaurants in Bacoor, Cavite according to Google Maps

Population and Sample Estimate

The researchers defined population in this study as all units with specific qualities that researchers are interested in examining. The target community or chosen group of people who are participating in this study is referred to as the population, according to the definition. As a result, the sample group for this study includes the following sorts of participants: restaurant chains, restaurant managers, and Bacoor residents.

The researchers in this study utilized purposeful sampling to choose participants. Purposive sampling is commonly utilized when there are a limited number of people who are knowledgeable about the topic under investigation or when the study is limited to a particular field or a small group. According to Steinke (2004), nonprobability sampling, such as purposive sampling, should not be utilized to obtain the same findings as probability sampling or held to the same quality standards.

Twenty-five (25) restaurant managers and twenty-five (25) restaurant customers were surveyed by the researchers in Bacoor, Cavite. Restaurant managers were chosen as respondents because they have an educational background in food management and customer satisfaction, allowing the researchers to gather correct information from the respondents.

The researchers simultaneously sent a survey questionnaire to twenty-five (25) restaurant managers and twenty-five (25) customers from any of the specified food venues. Anyone above the age of 18, whether a client or a restaurant manager in Bacoor, Cavite, can participate in the poll. Researchers created an online survey questionnaire and did a face-to-face survey to gather data from respondents.

Data Gathering

This research employed a quantitative approach. Data were collected using a quantitative technique by emailing a survey questionnaire. Through this, we can promote awareness and encourage edible food packaging using this way. The quantifiable data revealed how many consumers the researchers have product

information for, as well as how many consumers approved or disapproved of edible food packaging as a substitute for plastic food packaging. The goal of this project is to encourage restaurants and consumers to employ edible food packaging, such as edible straws. Because restaurant management has the potential to provide relevant food-related data, the researchers collected data with their help.

Restaurant managers were visited by researchers who will obtain their approval to perform the study. Once consents are given, the researchers will present a sample of EcoBiertos edible straws for them to analyze its sustainability. The researchers subsequently distributed surveys to gauge public opinion on edible straws, sustainability, and the chance of the straws to be utilized in restaurants or personal places.

Now, for restaurant customers, the researchers will approach them and ask for their consent to be respondents. If they agreed, we provided them with an edible tapioca rice straw from EcoBiertos, which they used with their drinks on the spot and analyzed via sensory evaluation before handing them the survey questionnaire. If the respondent is unavailable for a face-to-face survey, we could provide an alternative by contacting them via Messenger for their consent. The researchers have two options for sending the sample items to the customers: the first is to send the items via courier, and the second is to meet up with them. The replies from the online survey were examined using the Google Survey integrated tool as well as a face-to-face survey, which all adhered to COVID-19 protocols. The researchers and respondents adhered to all safety precautions and met in a non-congested location. Then, as soon as the sampled items arrived, a link to an online survey was emailed over Messenger, and the survey was completed using Google Forms.

Statistical Treatment of Data

A t-test is a statistical hypothesis test where the test statistic follows a student's t-distribution under the null hypothesis. A t-test is commonly employed when the value of a scaling component in the test statistic is known. The test statistics (under certain conditions) follow a student's t-distribution when the scaling term is unknown and replaced by a data-driven estimate.

Results

Figure 2 shows that there are sixteen females (11.44%), and fourteen male consumer respondents (14.56%), which make up 25 of the respondents. In Figure 3, it shows that there are sixteen male restaurant managers (16.64%), and there are only nine female restaurant managers (9.36%) as respondents.

Figure 2. Percent Distribution of Consumers by Sex

Figure 3. Percent Distribution of Restaurant Managers by Sex

Figure 4 shows that most of the consumers are between the range of 36 to 45 years old, while there is only one consumer who is from 18 to 25 years old. Meanwhile, 17.68% of the restaurant managers are 18 to 25 years old, and eight or 8.32% are between 26 to 35 years old (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Percent Distribution of Consumer by Age

Figure 5. Percent Distribution of Restaurant Managers by Age

Table 2 presents an average of 1.344 in which the customers are aware of edible straws and related products before the testing and survey. Customers with an age of between the ranges of 18 to 25 are aware of edible straws already, but customers above the age of 36 are not aware of edible straws and related products. Meanwhile, both male and female customers are both aware of edible straws and related products.

Table 3 shows that the average mean for restaurant managers on their awareness of edible straws and related products is 1.488, which means that the respondents are aware of edible straws. Restaurant managers ages 18 to 25, and 26 to 35; and those male and female respondents are all aware of edible straws and related products.

Table 2. Mean Score for the Awareness of Edible Straws of Customers

Demographic Profile		Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Explanation
Age	18-25	1.38	Yes	The customers are aware of edible straws and related products.
	36-45	0.60	No	The customers are not aware of edible straws and related products.
Sex	Male	1.45	Yes	The customers are aware of edible straws and related products.
	Female	1.25	Yes	The customers are aware of edible straws and related products.
Average		1.34	Yes	The customers are aware of edible straws and related products.

Table 3. Mean Score for the Awareness of Edible Straws of Restaurant Managers

Demographic Profile		Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Explanation
Age	18-25	1.41	Yes	The customers are aware of edible straws and related products.
	36-45	1.53	No	The customers are aware of edible straws and related products.
Sex	Male	1.31	Yes	The customers are aware of edible straws and related products.
	Female	1.69	Yes	The customers are aware of edible straws and related products.
Average		1.49	Yes	The customers are aware of edible straws and related products.

The mean average for the taste of Ecobiertos plastic straws is 3.856, as shown in Table 4, which means that the edible straw has a slight neutral taste to it and does not affect the taste of the drink. Respondents of age 18 to 25 answered that edible straws have a slight neutral taste to it and customers between the ranges of 26 to 35 answered that the straw has a neutral taste, and it does not affect the flavor of the liquid. Male customers responded that Ecobiertos edible straw has only a neutral taste, when compared to female customers who perceived that there is only a slight neutral taste to it.

Table 4. Mean Score for the Perception of Customers on the Taste of Ecobiertos Edible Straws

Demographic Profile		Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Explanation
Age	18-25	3.81	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a slight neutral taste to it.
	36-45	5.00	Strongly Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a neutral taste to it.
Sex	Male	3.36	Neutral	Ecobiertos edible straws have a slight neutral taste to it.
	Female	4.24	Strongly Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a neutral taste to it.
Average		3.86	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a slight neutral taste to it.

Table 5 shows that restaurant managers observe that Ecobiertos edible straws have a neutral taste to it and do not affect the taste of the drink (4.54 mean average). Respondents of both ages and sex all answered that the straw has a neutral taste, does not affect the flavor of the liquid, and does not affect the drinking experience.

Table 5. Mean Score for the Perception of Restaurant Managers on the Taste of Ecobiertos Edible Straws

Demographic Profile		Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Explanation
Age	18-25	4.58	Strongly Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a neutral taste to it.
	36-45	4.22	Strongly Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a neutral taste to it.
Sex	Male	4.58	Strongly Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a neutral taste to it.
	Female	4.47	Strongly Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a neutral taste to it.
Average		4.54	Strongly Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a neutral taste to it.

Table 6 shows that respondents observe that the edible straw has a slight odor that is neither strong nor pungent but is best described as a slight starch aroma which does not affect the experience, smell, and taste of the drink (Mean = 3.41). Customers who are between 18 to 25 years old responded that the edible straw has a slight odor, while respondents above the age of 36 perceived only a barely detectable odor from the straw. Female respondents discerned that the straw has a slight odor to it that is not strong and does not affect the experience from drinking with it, although male restaurant managers perceived that there is a slight odor present but is close to the smell of starch or flour.

Table 6. Mean Score for the Perception of Customers on the Odor of Ecobiertos Edible Straws

Demographic Profile		Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Explanation
Age	18-25	3.38	Neutral	Ecobiertos edible straws have a slight odor that is neither pungent nor pungent.
	36-45	4.20	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a very slight odor that is barely detectable.
Sex	Male	2.95	Neutral	Ecobiertos edible straws have a slight odor that is neither pungent nor pungent.
	Female	3.77	Neutral	Ecobiertos edible straws have a slight odor that is neither pungent nor pungent.
Average		3.41	Neutral	Ecobiertos edible straws have a slight odor that is neither pungent nor pungent.

Table 7 depicts that Ecobiertos edible straws has no detectable odor and does not affect the drinking experience from the straw (Mean = 4.344). Respondents of both ages noticed that the straw has no strong smell and is odorless, which has the same response from female restaurant managers. Male respondents, however, answered that the straw has a slight odor, but it still does not affect the taste nor the smell of the liquid.

Table 7. Mean Score for the Perception of Restaurant Managers on the Odor of Ecobiertos Edible Straws

Demographic Profile		Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Explanation
Age	18-25	4.34	Strongly Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have no detectable odor.
	36-45	4.35	Strongly Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have no detectable odor.
Sex	Male	4.20	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a very slight odor that is barely detectable.
	Female	4.60	Strongly Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have no detectable odor.
Average		4.34	Strongly Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have no detectable odor.

The mean average score of the perception of customers on the texture of Ecobiertos edible straws is 3.86 (Table 8), which means that the straw has a fine and smooth texture to it and is easy to grip and does not slip easily. Both ages and gender agree that the straw has a nice texture to it and is easy to hold when drinking.

Table 8. Mean Score for the Perception of Customers on the Texture of Ecobiertos Edible Straw

Demographic Profile	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Explanation
Age 18-25	3.86	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a smooth and easy grip to it.
36-45	3.80	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a smooth and easy grip to it.
Sex Male	3.64	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a smooth and easy grip to it.
Female	4.03	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a smooth and easy grip to it.
Average	3.86	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a smooth and easy grip to it.

The mean average for the restaurant managers on the texture of the edible straw is 4.03 (Table 9). The edible straw has to a degree a nice texture with a non-slip feature to it. Respondents of ages above the age of 26 answered that the straw has a very nice smooth and fine texture to it and does not slip when handling it.

Table 9. Mean Score for the Perception of Restaurant Managers on the Texture of Ecobiertos Edible Straw

Demographic Profile	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Explanation
Age 18-25	3.79	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a smooth and easy grip to it.
36-45	4.47	Strongly Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws are very smooth and have a great grip on it.
Sex Male	3.95	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a smooth and easy grip to it.
Female	4.20	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a smooth and easy grip to it.
Average	4.03	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a smooth and easy grip to it.

The mean score gathered from the customers is 4.064 (Table 2.7), which means that the respondents perceived the straw has a nice appeal to it but not as attractive as other plastic or metal straws. Female respondents and ages 36-45, had a more positive response seeing that the edible straws are appealing to the public, when compared to male respondents and ages 18-25, who perceived the straw as attractive but not as appealing as plastic straws.

Restaurant managers on their perception of the appearance of edible straws has a mean score of 4.48 (Table 11), which means that the edible straw is very appealing and attractive to the public. The reception of edible straws of male respondents is that the straw is appealing but not as quite as appealing as other straws made from plastic or metal.

Table 10. Mean Score for the Perception of Customers on the Appearance of Ecobiertos Edible Straws

Demographic Profile	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Explanation
Age 18-25	4.03	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a nice aesthetic appeal to it.
36-45	4.80	Strongly Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a very appealing aesthetic to it.
Sex Male	3.53	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a nice aesthetic appeal to it.
Female	4.49	Strongly Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a very appealing aesthetic to it.
Average	4.06	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a nice aesthetic appeal to it.

Table 11. Mean Score for the Perception of Restaurant Managers on the Appearance of Ecobiertos Edible Straws

Demographic Profile	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Explanation
Age 18-25	4.51	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a nice aesthetic appeal to it.
36-45	4.43	Strongly Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a very appealing aesthetic to it.
Sex Male	4.34	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a nice aesthetic appeal to it.
Female	4.73	Strongly Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a very appealing aesthetic to it.
Average	4.48	Agree	Ecobiertos edible straws have a nice aesthetic appeal to it.

Table 12 presents that the mean average is 4.368 for the reception of customers on the likelihood of buying Ecobiertos edible straws. It means that the respondents would likely purchase edible straws and other related products, not only from Ecobiertos but as well as other brands. There is a bit lower reception for male customers which decided to highly consider purchasing it rather than purchasing it.

Meanwhile, Table 13 has a mean average of 4.344, which shares the same description for the customers, where the respondents are highly likely to purchase the product without hesitation. Like with customers, only the male restaurant managers decided to consider it rather than purchasing it immediately.

Table 12. Mean Score for the Perception of Customers on the Likelihood of Purchasing Ecobiertos Edible Straws

Demographic Profile	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Explanation
Age 18-25	4.35	Strongly Agree	The respondent would likely purchase Ecobiertos edible straws and other brands.
36-45	4.80	Strongly Agree	The respondent would likely purchase Ecobiertos edible straws and other brands.
Sex Male	4.11	Agree	The respondent would consider purchasing Ecobiertos edible straws and other brands.
Female	4.57	Strongly Agree	The respondent would likely purchase Ecobiertos edible straws and other brands.
Average	4.37	Strongly Agree	The respondent would likely purchase Ecobiertos edible straws and other brands.

Table 13. Mean Score for the Perception of Restaurant Managers on the Likelihood of Purchasing of Ecobiertos Edible Straws

Demographic Profile		Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Explanation
Age	18-25	4.29	Strongly Agree	The respondent would likely purchase Ecobiertos edible straws and other brands.
	36-45	4.45	Strongly Agree	The respondent would likely purchase Ecobiertos edible straws and other brands.
Sex	Male	4.19	Agree	The respondent would consider purchasing Ecobiertos edible straws and other brands.
	Female	4.62	Strongly Agree	The respondent would likely purchase Ecobiertos edible straws and other brands.
Average		4.34	Strongly Agree	The respondent would likely purchase Ecobiertos edible straws and other brands.

Customers and restaurant managers are likely to be receptive in promotion strategies of edible straws (Table 14). The best strategy to employ on customers is a mix are exclusive previews, as well as product testing, special introductory offers, which is not limited to discounts and promotions, product website, complementary upgrade like buy-one take-one promotion, reviews from other consumers and product testers, and advertising in Google and Facebook, as well as in other social media platforms. This is quite like target restaurant managers but without special introductory offers. There are better ways to promote edible straws, but every strategy is effective as the respondents are likely to purchase the product through one of the employed strategies.

The p-value for the awareness on Ecobiertos edible straw (Table 15) is 0.5675, which is greater than the α -level of 0.05, therefore we accept the Ho (null hypothesis) that there is no significant difference between customers and restaurant managers. It means that the results of customers and restaurant managers is the same or almost the same, therefore, both are aware of edible straws and related products.

The p-value for the taste of Ecobiertos edible straw (Table 16) is 0.0094 which is lesser than the α -level of 0.05, therefore we reject the Ho (null hypothesis) that there is a significant difference between customers and restaurant managers. It means that the results of customers and restaurant managers are different from one another, therefore, the groups A (customer/consumer) and B (restaurant managers) have different results on the taste of Ecobiertos edible straws.

Table 14. Mean Average of Promotion Strategies Effectiveness

Promotion Strategy	Customers				Restaurant Managers			
	Age		Sex		Age		Sex	
	16-25	36-45	Male	Female	16-25	36-45	Male	Female
Exclusive previews and product testing	4.38	5.00	4.00	4.71	4.4706	4.875	4.625	4.5556
Special introductory offers	4.42	4.00	3.91	4.79	4.2353	4.25	4.1875	4.3333
E-mail newsletters	3.67	4.00	4.00	3.43	4.1765	4.375	4	4.6667
Product website	4.38	4.00	4.00	4.64	4.4118	4.625	4.3125	4.7778
Product launch events	4.04	4.00	4.18	3.93	4.0588	4.375	3.9375	4.5556
Complimentary upgrade	4.33	5.00	4.09	4.57	4.4118	4.365	4.3125	4.7778
Trade-in product	4.00	4.00	3.45	4.43	4.0588	4.5	4.0625	4.4444
Product reviews from customers and testers	4.46	5.00	4.36	4.57	4.6471	4.625	4.5	4.8889
Google advertising	4.42	5.00	4.18	4.64	4.5294	4.75	4.5	4.7778
Facebook advertising	4.30	5.00	3.91	4.64	4.5294	4.75	4.5	4.7778
Average	4.24	4.50	4.01	4.44	4.3529	4.575	4.2936	4.6556
General Average	4.25				4.42			

Table 15. Significant Difference of the Awareness on Ecobiertos Edible Straw

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.08	1	0.08	0.3314	0.567525	4.042652
Within Groups	11.5872	48	0.2414			
Total	11.6672	49				

Table 16. Significant Difference of the Taste on Ecobiertos Edible Straw

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	6.0552	1	6.0552	7.313043	0.009443	4.042652
Within Groups	39.744	48	0.828			
Total	45.7992	49				

The p-value for the odor of Ecobiertos edible straw is 0.0003 which is lesser than the α -level of 0.05, therefore we reject the H_0 (null hypothesis) that there is a significant difference between customers and restaurant managers. It means that the results of customers and restaurant managers are different from one another, therefore, the groups A (customer/consumer) and B (restaurant managers) have different results on the odor of Ecobiertos edible straws.

Table 17. Significant Difference of the Odor on Ecobiertos Edible Straw

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	10.9512	1	10.9512	15.07046	0.000316	4.042652
Within Groups	34.88	48	0.726667			
Total	45.8312	49				

The p-value for the texture of the Ecobiertos edible straw is 0.4036 which is greater than the α -level of 0.05, therefore we accept the H_0 (null hypothesis) that there are no significant differences between customers and restaurant managers. It means that the results of customers and restaurant managers are the same or almost the same, therefore, both agree on the texture of Ecobiertos edible straw.

Table 18. Significant Difference of the Texture on Ecobiertos Edible Straw

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.3872	1	0.3872	0.710024	0.403615	4.042652
Within Groups	26.176	48	0.545333			
Total	26.5632	49				

The p-value for the appearance of Ecobiertos edible straw is 0.0395 which is lesser than the α -level of 0.05, therefore we reject the H_0 (null hypothesis) that there is a significant difference between customers and restaurant managers. It means that the results of customers and restaurant managers are different from one another, therefore, the groups A (customer/consumer) and B (restaurant managers) have different results on the appearance of Ecobiertos edible straws.

Table 19. Significant Difference of the Appearance on Ecobiertos Edible Straw

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	2.1632	1	2.1632	4.479912	0.039506	4.042652
Within Groups	23.1776	48	0.482867			
Total	25.3408	49				

The p-value for the likelihood of purchase of the Ecobiertos edible straw is 0.9036 which is greater than the α -level of 0.05, therefore we accept the Ho (null hypothesis) that there are no significant differences between customers and restaurant managers. It means that the results of customers and restaurant managers are the same or almost the same, therefore, both agree on the likelihood of purchase of Ecobiertos edible straw.

Table 20. Significant Difference of the Likelihood of Purchase on Ecobiertos Edible Straw

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.0072	1	0.0072	0.014835	0.903566	4.042652
Within Groups	23.296	48	0.485333			
Total	23.3032	49				

The p-value for the effectiveness of promotion strategy for Ecobiertos edible straw is 0.1698 which is greater than the α -level of 0.05, therefore we accept the Ho (null hypothesis) that there are no significant differences between customers and restaurant managers. It means that the results of customers and restaurant managers are the same or almost the same, therefore, both agree on the effectiveness of promotion strategy for Ecobiertos edible straw.

Table 21. Significant Difference of the Promotion Strategy Effectiveness on Ecobiertos Edible Straw

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.6728	1	0.6728	1.942637	0.169802	4.042652
Within Groups	16.624	48	0.346333			
Total	17.2968	49				

Discussion

Our hypotheses have indicated that, based on the perspectives of most of our participants, who are consumers and food industry managers, there is no significant difference in the acceptability of the usage of Ecobiertos edible straws. According to the data, edible straws received overwhelmingly good feedback and acceptance from both customers and food industry managers. They assessed the edible straw as having a wonderful appeal with an almost odorless and tasteless quality to it that does not interfere with the sipping experience.

The edible straw also has a non-slip, silky, and fine texture with a subtle rice or flour fragrance like dried pasta. Some respondents also stated that edible straws are a much more effective replacement for plastic straws and paper straws, as paper straws often become soggy and compromise the quality of drinking in restaurants and food enterprises. To some extent, the participants of the study are already aware of edible straws and other biodegradable and environmentally friendly products. Some already use biodegradable materials, such as compostable utensils and recycled paper cups. Participants have a favorable impression about edible straws.

Before being evaluated on its merits, the respondents were given the opportunity to use the Ecobiertos edible straw. The edible straws were reported as tasteless by the participants, with some having a trace of rice or wheat to it that is best described as a dried spaghetti noodle flavor to it. They also perceive a faint earthy aroma that reminds them of uncooked spaghetti. Participants also stated that they will most likely purchase Ecobiertos edible straws and other comparable items following the testing.

Finally, based on the findings, the promotion strategy for edible straws should be further investigated. Respondents are open to diverse tactics and procedures for implementing product promotion initiatives. They also stated that it will raise awareness of its more environmentally friendly qualities as compared to paper straws.

This study aims to provide an alternative to plastic using edible food items. The researchers want to promote edible food items to provide knowledge and awareness of their existence because solid waste material is one of the biggest threats to our environment, and it does not only affect nature but living things as well. That is why fundamental development in food packaging should be made to strengthen environmental protection and to recognize and solve a severe environmental problem.

Conclusion

A total of 50 respondents in Bacoor, Cavite took part in this study, which was divided into two groups. Each group comprises 25 samples and is divided into two categories: consumers and managers. In terms of age, there is only one respondent that is between the ranges of 36 and 45 for the customers, with the rest being from the ages of 18 to 25 years old. Meanwhile, the study gathered seventeen respondents from the ages of 18 to 25 and eight respondents from the ages of 26 to 35, representing the managers. There are sixteen female, and fourteen male respondents gathered to represent the consumers that make up the 25 of the sample. There are sixteen male food business managers gathered from the survey, and there are only nine female food business managers gathered for the research as respondents. They have similar or nearly identical findings, indicating that both are aware of edible straws and related products.

Exclusive previews and product testing, special introductory offers, including discounts and promotions, product websites, complementary upgrades such as buy-one-take-one promotions, reviews from other consumers and product testers, and advertising on Google and Facebook, as well as other social media platforms, are the best strategies to employ on customers. This is comparable to targeting food business managers, except there are no special introductory deals. To summarize, there are superior ways to promote edible straws, yet each strategy is effective because respondents are more inclined to acquire the product using one of the used strategies.

Subsequently, edible straws garnered enormously positive comments and acceptance from both customers and food sector executives. They thought the edible straw was lovely, with an almost odorless and tasteless quality that did not interfere with the sipping experience. The edible straw has a non-slip, silky, and delicate texture, as well as a slight rice or flour scent that is akin to dried pasta. Edible straws could pioneer in replacing paper and plastic straws soon and helping other products like mushroom Styrofoam, reed and bamboo straws, wheat and barley utensils, and renewed and recycled paper packaging materials without plastic linings.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions, the researchers concluded that changes must be made in the food establishments in the Philippines, and operational alterations would make the environment refrain from degradation in the long run. The researchers outline their suggested reforms as well as frameworks for our recommendation. The researchers will present product packaging structure with enhancements to consumers to widen the range of information to be given to consumers, which maintains the identity and functions of existing products but introduces sustainable edible desirable features for a plastic-free packaging that will benefit the environment. To recognize and solve significant environmental risks, fundamental advancements in food packaging should be made to strengthen environmental protection. Researchers aimed to present the conceptual frameworks, which began with an analysis of existing packaging, progressed on to a presentation of a new packaging, and ended with proposed plastic-free products to obtain optimum safety for consumers. Considering the findings of the study, the researchers make the following recommendations to future researchers:

- Collaborate with edible food packaging companies such as Loliware and Evoware to obtain seaweed-based edible packaging and cups.

- Collaborate immediately to get approval from the company.
- Use edible cups and straws for other products to test their effectiveness.
- Present enhanced product packaging structure.

The researchers recommend enhancing future research in the food industry, addressing specific weak points, and recognizing that the current study should broaden our understanding of and ability to recognize environmental components in innovating products, especially with plastic, and deepen our understanding of how plastic is transported between components and improve our knowledge of its effect on the environment.

For future researchers that will conduct the same or similar study, the researchers recommend that they can use other edible components in terms of packaging aside from straw. It would be better if the future researchers would gather data from different perspectives, or they could interview managers for them to get the information that would be useful to the study that they are going to conduct. To improve the study, the researchers recommend using social media platforms to implement the advantages of edible packaging to educate consumers, create an interaction, and give facts that are not just knowledgeable but also visually appealing. The researcher thinks that it would be good to get the opinions of consumers and managers. Lastly, the most important of all is to provide an interactive and informative forum that is considerate and respectful to both parties and individuals.

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